

An Economic Analysis of Women Empowerment Thoughts SHGs Progress and Way Forward

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Introduction

Social mobilization through “self-Groups” is inevitable for economic empowerment and poverty alleviation. The concept of “Self- help Group” exist prior to any intervention. The member are linked by a common bond like caste, blood, community and place of origin or activity in these natural groups of ‘affinity groups’. It is imperative that the self- help group should be promoted in the way that facilities a cooperative, participative and empowerment culture.

The ‘self-help groups’ provide economic benefits areas of production process by undertaking common action programs, like cost- effective credit delivery system, generation a forum for collective, learning with rural people, promoting democratic culture, fostering an entrepreneurial culture, proving a firm base for dialogue and cooperation in programs with other institutions, possessing credibility and power to ensure participation and helping to assess an individual member’s management capacity.

Self Help Groups enhance the equality of status of women as participants, decision- maker and beneficiaries in the democratic, economic, social and cultural spheres of life. The SHGs has inculcated a great confidence in the minds of rural women to succeed in their day to day life. This study aims at saving and rural credit of SHGs in three villages from Tirunelveli District., Kalakad, nangunari, panagudi.

Size of SHGs

The size of the SHGs should range from 10 members to 20 members, and if it exceeds 20 members in the group. It must be registered under the Registration Act. Each group conducts a regular meeting once in a week and generally they are held on every Sunday.

Objectives

The overall objective of the present study is to analysis the economic empowerment of women through SHGs in three villages from Tirunelveli District. However more specifically:

1. To examine the size and pattern of SHGs
2. To know the reasons for joining SHGs and
3. To study the income, expenditure and savings of the members after joining SHGs.
4. To analyze the role o SHGs in providing rural credit.
5. Methodology.
6. To evaluate the performance of the Self Help Groups in Udangudi Town Panchayat.
7. To analyse the impact of micro-credit on socio-economic empowerment of women in the study area.
8. To study the major income generating activities of Self Help Groups.

Economic Status of the udangudi Panchayat Union

The Union panchayat has all rural population, and it is one of the reasons for its backwardness. The percentage of the literates in the union panchayat is 72.85. It is higher than to other nearby union panchayat in Tuticorin District.

Agriculture is the main source of income in this Panchayat Union. The cultivators and agricultural labourers both together accounts for 35.45 per cent of the total work force of the panchayat. Udangudi has been identified as the most ideal place for banana cultivation. In Udangudi panchayat union 20 per cent of the population is working under the various government institutions in across Tamil Nadu. This is due to the increase in the awareness of the people for education.

The union accounts for 11 per cent of the district total area under Banana cultivation. The cultivation of horicultural crops, fruits and a vegetable is in an upward trend, as the local farmers show interest in earning of profits. The large number of existence of Palmyra and Coconut trees in the panchayat has bright prospects for development of industries based on these to improve the rural economy.

Status of the women after the SHGs

From the survey conducted the following points were revealed:

After the formation they are economically viable and living status has improved.

It is observed that owing to increased in the level in income, the children of some of the members could continue their studies by paying school fees regularly.

This scheme helps them to get relieved from the clutches of money lenders.

Suggestions

1. Regular attendance of members is a must for efficient functioning of SHGs.
2. Active participation of members is vital for efficient functioning of SHGs.
3. Literacy level should be increased.
4. Mobilization of rural savings through encouragement is needed.
5. Economic empowerments of women will be possible if more SHGs as many of them complained that they do not know about bank interest rates.
6. Bank interest may be reduced.
7. SHGs is can be used it promote small family norms, mobilization small savings and other social works.

There is need to accept that women's needs are not only for self-employment.

The Programmes should be designed on the basis of the needs of women at the micro level. Planning for self-employment for women needs a multipronged strategy.

Proper monitoring of groups needs to be done at various stages of their growth. Strengthening and Group monitoring methods including selection of leader, homogeneity of Group members, etc. need to be developed.

Group activity needs to be encouraged in the interest of building up of strong SHGs. Selection of the leader needs to be done carefully.

Training needs to be imparted in a systematic manner, covering groups according to some schedule or roster. As trainings are different kinds i.e. basic leadership and vocational, it is essential to draw up a plan according to the specific requirements of each groups. The training programmes should be organized in nearby places which are convenient to the members.

Should provide subsidy loan for Agriculture Women SHGs for innovative projects.

Should provide self employment loan for individual SHGs members.

Loan repayment should be flexible based on their varying levels of income and savings.

The SHGs linkages show that majority of them have been linked to banks and NGOs but there is need to increase the SHGs access to the supply chain, linkages to markets and appropriate technologies.

The training or skill up gradation of the members is essential to successfully run the SHGs. Skill development of women will enable them to take up enterprises and thereby contribute more to their family income.

The SHGs by encouraging members to take up income generating activities have

helped in increasing the employment opportunities. Hence, encouragement and support by the government to establish SHGs will certainly solve the problem of rural unemployment.

The government department should make budgetary allocation for training components for the Self Help Group members.

Conclusion

The micro credit summit (1997) held at Washington has stressed on provision for credit to 100 million world's poorest families to overcome the problems of underemployment and poverty. Micro finance can play a crucial role in achieving Millennium Development Goals and reducing world's poverty by 50 per cent by the end of 2015. India is the home to 22 per cent of the world's poor. Poverty reduction is only possible by providing easy access to credit for small entrepreneurial activities. Considering the vast number of poor, discriminated and underprivileged women and the need of financial services, there is tremendous scope for micro financing through SHGs in India. Empowering women is not just for meeting their economic needs but also more holistic social development. The SHGs empower women and train them to take active part in socio-economic progress of the nation. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru said, "To awaken the people, it is women who must be awakened; once she is on the move, the family moves, the village moves and nation moves". Now the women are awakened by the Self Help Groups and Financial Inclusion can be achieved.